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Aphid species of the family Adelgidae (Hemiptera: Adelgoidea) in Lithuania: an overview

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Abstract: According to the reference data (1916–2010) and more recent (2017–2018) research, eleven species of the family Adelgidae were included in the faunal list of Lithuania. The most common species from 1916 onwards appear those of the *Adelges laricis - tardus* species complex, mostly reported due to their economic importance. Other common species are those of the *Sacchiphantes abietis - viridis* species complex. *Aphrastasia pectinatae* was reported from 1965 onwards as injuring several species of the genus *Abies*: *A. alba*, *A. balsamea*, *A. concolor*, *A. holophylla*, *A. lasiocarpa* var. *arizonica*, *A. nordmanniana*, *A. sibirica*, *A. veitchii* throughout Lithuania. *Dreyfusia piceae* was reported as a common pest of *Abies alba* in urban plantings and botanical gardens onwards from 1991. *Pineus pini* recently increased in numbers turning to be the widespread species in Lithuania endangering young pine stands. In 2017–2018, *Gilletteella cooleyi*, *Cholodkovskya viridana*, *Pineus orientalis* and *P. cembrae* were added to the list. Information on the life cycles and host specificity of Lithuanian populations and comparison of their partial sequences of mitochondrial COI with samples from other European countries is presented.

Key words: Adelgidae; aphids; species identification; systematics; coniferous trees; Lithuania; mitochondrial COI.

Introduction

Aphids of the family Adelgidae Annand 1928 (Hemiptera, Sternorrhyncha, Aphidomorpha, Adelgoidea) are phloem feeding insects inhabiting coniferous plants of family Pinaceae. Adelgids, like their host plants, are originally associated with the boreal and temperate regions of the Northern Hemisphere. An extraordinary feature of adelgid aphids is a two-year life cycle, with some species alternating between spruce (*Picea*) as a primary host plants and species of another conifer genera (*Abies*, *Larix*, *Pinus*, *Pseudotsuga*, *Tsuga*) as a secondary host plants. Some species do not alternate hosts, feeding only on *Picea* or one of the other conifer genera. Another striking characteristic of adelgids is their obligate oviparity. That is, Adelgidae species reproduce by laying eggs (both parthenogenetic and fertilized),

unlike most of the other aphid species that only lay fertilized eggs, but apply viviparity for parthenogenetic reproduction. Adelgid species are also famous by their ability to enforce their host plants to produce galls. Galls are formed from spruce buds when the developing needles enlarge laterally and their margins merge into each other, forming multiple chambers where the insects feed. Some galls appear species-specific enabling identification of the aphid species in the field (ANNAND 1928, BÖRNER & HEINZE 1957, HAVILL & FOOTTIT 2007, www.aphidsonworldsplants.info). Due to substantial impact on the development of their host plants, some adelgid species are important forestry pests, e.g. the hemlock woolly adelgid, *Annandina tsugae*, and the balsam woolly adelgid, *Dreyfusia piceae*. All this explains the relatively long and rich history of adelgid research. Nonetheless, there remain much controversy concerning biology, systematics and evolutionary history of adelgids (FOOTTIT *et al.* 2009, HAVILL *et al.* 2007, TOENSHOFF *et al.* 2012a, FAVRET *et al.* 2015, ALBRECHT 2017, www.aphidsonworldsplants.info). Based on European tradition (BÖRNER & HEINZE 1957, BINAZZI 1984, LAMPEL & MEIER 2003, NIETO NAFRIA *et al.* 2004, ŽUROVCOVÁ *et al.* 2010, OSIADACZ & HALAJ 2010) we use the classification system that distinguish several genera of Adelgidae. All they are available in Europe comprising 23 species altogether: *Adelges* (5 species), *Cholodkovskya* (2), *Sacchiphantes* (3), *Dreyfusia* (5), *Aphrastasia* (1), *Gilletteella* (2) and *Pineus* (5).

Forests comprise approximately 30% of Lithuania. Most of the forests are the pine and spruce stands (http://www.gmu.lt/forest_resources/), favorable for adelgids. Yet reference information about Adelgidae species composition and ecological specificity in Lithuania is insufficient and concerns fragmentary faunistic and pest management data reporting eight species available in Lithuania (JURONIS 2003, RAKAUSKAS *et al.* 2008, ŽUROVCOVÁ *et al.* 2010, for earlier references see RAKAUSKAS *et al.* 1992). For comparison, 17 species were reported from Czech Republic (ŽUROVCOVÁ *et al.* 2010) and Poland (OSIADACZ & HALAJ 2010, WOJCIECHOWSKI *et al.* 2015), 12 from Latvia (RUPAIS 1989). To enable successful management of the local aphid species, regional species diversity and ecological specificity should be properly evaluated. Ecological and evolutionary relationships as well as taxonomy of Adelgidae species are still not clear and demand further studies in different parts of the distribution area of this aphid family. The application of DNA-based methods applied for species delimitation and speciation process studies of Adelgidae did not allow resolving all taxonomic cases (HAVILL *et al.* 2007, FOOTTIT *et al.* 2009, ŽUROVCOVÁ *et al.* 2010, TOENSHOFF *et al.* 2012a). In this study, partial COI sequences were used to confirm ecology and morphology-based identification of Lithuanian adelgid species as well as for the investigation of their genetic diversity and relationships with samples collected in other European countries.

The aim of this work was to summarize available information concerning Adelgidae species of Lithuania.

Material and methods

Sampling and identification of morphological species

Aphid material has been collected in 2017-2018 in Lithuania and included 191 samples. Those used for the aims of this paper are listed in **Table 1**. The entire list of samples is available from the authors on the request. Microscope slides in Canada balsam were prepared according to BLACKMAN & EASTOP (1984) (fundatrices and gallicolae) and Jan Havelka's modified method for first instar larvae (mounting in Canada balsam after staining in Acid Fuchsin Stain). Aphid material is deposited at the Institute of Entomology of the Biology Centre (Czech Academy of Sciences) and Life Sciences Centre of the Vilnius University

(Lithuania). Keys of BLACKMAN & EASTOP (www.aphidsonworldsplants.info) and ALBRECHT (2017) were used for identification. When using morphological characters for species diagnoses, the problem is that several groups of Adelgidae species have similar or identical morphologies but different life cycles. For example, *Sacchiphantes viridis*, which alternates between *Picea* and *Larix*, is morphologically similar both to *S. abietis*, which is anholocyclic on *Picea*, and to *S. segregis*, which is anholocyclic on *Larix*. Therefore, one can hardly rely on pure morphology to identify adelgid species; ecological data (host plant and season) provide important additional information. On the other hand, anholocyclic populations of aphid species might be taken for host races or host-specific subspecies of the same species (STEFFAN 1970, BLACKMAN 1974, SHAPOSHNIKOV 1981, GULDEMOND 1990, BLACKMAN & BROWN 1991). When concerning reference data for Lithuanian Adelgidae, they are mostly based on such ecological information (host plant and season data), microscope preparations absent. Therefore, they are impossible to verify. Another problem is that principal morphological characters for species recognition are the shape and distribution of the dorsal sclerites, wax plates, and wax glands of the first-instar larvae that are not easy to find and aphid material demands sophisticated microscope preparations technique ([WWW.APHIDSONWORLDSPLANTS.INFO](http://www.aphidsonworldsplants.info), ALBRECHT 2017). Interspecific morphological differences are less apparent in adult insects (ANNAND 1928, BINAZZI 2000). Therefore, partial sequences of mitochondrial COI of the same samples were used in our study to verify the morphological identification of samples.

DNA isolation, amplification, sequencing and data analysis

For molecular analysis, several aphid individuals sampled from one colony were considered as a unique sample. Total genomic DNA was extracted using DNeasy Blood & Tissue kit (Qiagen). For the amplification of COI fragments primers 911-F and 912-R (TOENSHOFF *et al.* 2012a) were used. PCR amplification was carried out in a thermal cycler (Eppendorf) in 50 µl volumes containing 2 µl genomic DNA, 5 µl of each primer (1 µM), 25 µl of PCR master mix (Thermo Scientific) and 13 µl of nuclease free water (Thermo Scientific). The cycling parameters were as follows: denaturizing at 95°C for 4 min (1 cycle), denaturizing at 95°C for 45 s, annealing at 50°C for 45 s, extension at 72°C for 1 min 30 s (35 cycles in total), and final extension at 72°C for 10 min (1 cycle). PCR products were purified with Gene Jet PCR purification kit (Thermo Scientific) and sequenced at MacroGen Europe (Amsterdam, the Netherlands). The amplification primers were also used as sequencing primers. DNA sequences for each sample were confirmed with both sense and anti-sense strands and aligned in the BioEdit Sequence Alignment Editor (HALL 1999). Partial COI sequences were tested for stop codons and none were found. GenBank Accession numbers for each sample are given in **Table 1**.

Additional sequences for comparison were downloaded from GenBank (**Table 2**). Sequences were collapsed into haplotypes using FaBox 1.41 (VILLESEN 2007). To evaluate within-species sequence diversity uncorrected p-distances were calculated with MEGA 7 (KUMAR *et al.* 2016) and statistical parsimony networks with 95 % implemented connection limit were built using TCS v 1.21.

Results and discussion

Eleven aphid species of the family Adelgidae were detected in 2017-2018 in Lithuania. Four of them (asterisked in the list below) are new for Lithuania. Currently available information concerning distribution, biology and economic importance of Lithuanian species is given below together with available reference information after <http://www.faunaeur.org>, [HTTP://WWW.APHIDSONWORLDSPLANTS.INFO](http://www.aphidsonworldsplants.info), NIETO NAFRIA *et al.* 2004, ALBRECHT 2017.

Adelges laricis (VALLOT, 1836)

Common European species alternating between *Picea* and *Larix*. There is still controversy concerning taxonomic status of morphologically similar species anholocyclic on *Picea* (*A. tardus*, *A. geniculatus*, *A. lapponicus*). Reference data from Lithuania go back to the beginning of the last century. Numerous findings of galls on *Picea excelsa* (= *P. abies*) were reported from Anykščiai (TRZEBINSKI 1916), Trakai (OSTROWSKI 1927), and Vilnius (MOVŠOVIČIUS 1941) Counties of Baltic Highlands geographical region of Lithuania. These reports might actually concern *A. tardus* (see below). Our samples were both from *Picea abies* and *Larix* throughout all geographical regions of Lithuania, except Southeastern Plain.

Adelges tardus (DREYFUS, 1888)

Common European species anholocyclic on *Picea*. Apart from different life cycle, galls of this species open later than those of *A. laricis* (August-September against June-July). Morphological differences inconspicuous, COI sequences fail to recognize these species (ŽUROVCOVÁ *et al.* 2010). Earliest reference concerning this species in Lithuania is from *Picea abies* in Kaunas County of Middle Lithuanian Lowlands region (RUPAIS & JURONIS 1983). The earlier references (OSTROWSKI 1927, MOVŠOVIČIUS 1941) reporting numerous galls of *A. laricis* from *Picea excelsa* (= *P. abies*) late in the season (end of July and August) might concern in fact *A. tardus*. Our samples were from *Picea abies* throughout all geographical regions of Lithuania. We used 17 partial COI sequences (657 bp) extracted from Lithuanian *Adelges* species samples, together with 15 of downloaded sequences (Table 2) in our analyses. Average proportion of differences (p-distances) within *Adelges* species was 0.43% (Table 3). Thirteen haplotypes were detected in this species complex, differing by 1-12 substitutions (Fig. 1). Out of Lithuanian COI haplotypes, 5 of them (H9-H13) were unique, while others were the same with samples from Czech Republic (H1, H2, H5) and Austria (H1). Current knowledge suggests the conclusion that *A. laricis* and *A. tardus* (together with *A. geniculatus* and *A. lapponicus*) should be treated as subspecies or host races of the same species.

Aphrastasia pectinatae (CHOLODKOVSKY, 1888)

This species has been already registered in Finland, Scandinavian Peninsula, Latvia, Czech Republic, Poland, Ukraine and Romania. Holocyclic alternating between *Picea* spp. and *Abies* spp., anholocyclic lineages reported from Finland and Latvia. First reference reporting this species as a pest of *Abies balsamea*, *A. arizonica* and *A. concolor* in Coastal Lowland (Klaipėda County), Middle Lithuanian Lowland (Kaunas) and Baltic Highlands (Vilnius) geographical regions of Lithuania was made by RUPAIS (1965), followed by RUPAIS & JURONIS (1983) on *A. balsamea* for Kaunas. JURONIS (2003) reported this species as a common and dangerous pest of eight species of firs in Kaunas botanical gardens in 1998-2002 together with information on the presence of this species in Šiauliai and Panevėžys Counties (Middle Lithuanian Lowland). He also concerned the life cycle of *Aphrastasia pectinatae* in Kaunas botanical gardens suggesting it being anholocyclic on firs. Our samples were from *Abies* (*A. balsamea*, *A. concolor*, *A. lasiocarpa*) throughout all geographical regions of Lithuania, except Samogitian Upland and Southeastern Plain. We used 2 partial COI sequences (657 bp) extracted from Lithuanian samples, together with 1 of downloaded sequences (Table 2) in our analyses. Average proportion of differences (p-distances) within this species was 0.30% (Table 3). Two haplotypes were detected, differing by 1-3 substitutions (Fig. 1). Out of Lithuanian COI haplotypes, 1 of them (H2) was unique, while the other one was the same with samples from Czech Republic.

Fig. 1. Haplotype networks for partial COI sequences (657 bp, 95% connection limit, gaps treated as missing data) of 11 species of the family Adelgidae. The haplotype with the highest outgroup probability is displayed as a square, while others are displayed as ovals. For sample information, see Tables 1 and 3. AT – Austria, CZ – Czech Republic, DE – Germany, IT – Italy, LT – Lithuania.

***Cholodkovskya viridana** (CHOLODKOVSKY, 1896)

Common throughout Europe. Anholocyclic on *Larix* spp., feeding on needles in summer, overwintering in bark crevices on the stem. New finding for the fauna of Lithuania. Our samples were from *Larix kaempferi* and *Larix* sp. in Coastal Lowland of Lithuania (Klaipėda County and Curonian spit). We used 4 partial COI sequences (657 bp) extracted from Lithuanian samples, together with 3 of downloaded sequences (Table 2) in our analyses. Average proportion of differences (p-distances) within this species was 0.38% (Table 3). Three haplotypes were detected, differing by 2-8 substitutions (Fig. 1). Out of Lithuanian COI haplotypes, 2 of them (H2, H3) were unique, while H1 was the same with samples from Czech Republic.

Dreyfusia piceae (RATZEBURG, 1844)

Common European species, anholocyclic on *Abies* spp., infesting trunk and larger branches of older trees. North American populations use to exploit stems and buds of the crown region of *A. balsamea* and *A. fraseri*, causing extensive injury. Taxonomically is close to *D. nordmanniana* which is host alternating between *Picea orientalis* and *Abies* spp. Molecular phylogenetic studies based on mitochondrial (COI and Cytb) and nuclear (EF1 α) markers failed to find any consistent differences between *D. nordmanniana*, *D. piceae* and *D. prelli* (ŽUROVCOVÁ *et al.* 2010, RAVN *et al.* 2013). In Lithuania, it was

reported by JURONIS (2003) as pest of *Abies alba* in 1991-1992 in Kaunas botanical gardens and urban plantings of Kaunas (Middle Lithuanian Lowland), also in Vilnius (Baltic Highlands). The author suggested the observed population of this species in Kaunas botanical gardens being anholocyclic. Our samples were from *A. veitchii* and *A. alba* in Coastal Lowland of Lithuania (Klaipėda County and Curonian spit) and Samogitian Upland (Plungė County). We used 3 partial COI sequences (657 bp) extracted from Lithuanian samples, together with 11 of downloaded sequences (**Table 2**) in our analyses. Average proportion of differences (p-distances) within *Dreyfusia* species was 0.19% (**Table 3**). Four haplotypes were detected in this species complex, differing by 1-5 substitutions. (**Fig. 1**). Out of Lithuanian COI haplotypes, 2 of them (H1, H4) were the same with samples from Czech Republic and Austria. Available information suggests *D. nordmanniana* and *D. piceae* (together with *D. prelli*) being subspecies or host races of the same species. Lithuanian findings of *Dreyfusia* were exclusively from *Abies* spp., suggesting all them being *D. piceae*.

**Gilletteella cooleyi* (GILLETTE, 1907)

Holocyclic alternating between *Picea* spp. and *Pseudotsuga* spp. Native to western North America, but now occurring throughout Europe, might harm *Pseudotsuga*. There is still controversy concerning taxonomic status of anholocyclic populations of this species (see below). New finding for the fauna of Lithuania. Our samples of *Gilletteella* from *Picea pungens* were in the Middle Lithuanian Lowland (Pakruojis County), Baltic Highlands (Utena and Vilnius Counties), and Southeastern Plain (Lazdijai County). Our samples of *Gilletteella* from *Pseudotsuga* were in the Coastal Lowland (Klaipėda County and Curonian spit), Samogitian Upland (Telšiai County), Middle Lithuanian Lowland (Raseiniai, Tauragė, Radviliškis, Joniškis, Pakruojis, Panevėžys Counties), Baltic Highlands (Anykščiai, Utena, Zarasai, Molėtai, Rokiškis, Ignalina Counties) and Southeastern Plain (Lazdijai County). We used 7 partial COI sequences (652 bp) extracted from Lithuanian samples, together with 11 of downloaded sequences (**Table 2**) in our analyses. Average proportion of differences (p-distances) within *Gilletteella* species was 0.19% (**Table 3**). Five haplotypes were detected in this species complex, differing by 1-6 substitutions (**Fig. 1**). Out of Lithuanian COI haplotypes, 1 of them (H5) was unique, while the other one (H1) was the same with samples from Czech Republic. Current knowledge suggests the conclusion that *G. coweni* and *G. cooleyi* (together with non-galling, anholocyclic form of *G. cooleyi* on *Picea glauca* in Canada) should be treated as subspecies or host races of the same species ([HTTP://WWW.APHIDSONWORLDSPLANTS.INFO](http://www.aphidsonworldsplants.info), TOENSHOFF *et al.* 2012a). Based on our findings of *Gilletteella* on *Pseudotsuga* in the Curonian spit (no findings on *Picea pungens* despite special numerous efforts there) the existence of the anholocyclic *Gilletteella coweni* in Lithuania cannot be excluded. *Gilletteella coweni* (GILLETTE, 1907) is native to western North America, but now occurring throughout Europe. It was reported as a pest from Italy (ROVERSI & BINAZZI 1996).

**Pinus cembra* (CHOLODKOVSKY, 1888).

Common in boreo – alpine regions of Europe. Host alternating between *Picea* spp. and *Pinus* (*P. cembra*, *P. pumila*, *P. koraiensis*, *P. sibirica*). Anholocyclic lineages on *Pinus* were reported from Finland. New finding for the fauna of Lithuania. Our samples were from *Pinus cembra* in Baltic Highlands (Vilnius County) and Middle Lithuanian Lowland (Kėdainiai County) and from *Pinus sibirica* in Coastal Lowland (Klaipėda County). We used 2 partial COI sequences (657 bp) extracted from Lithuanian samples, together with 5 of downloaded sequences (**Table 2**) in our analyses. Average proportion of differences

(p-distances) within this species species was 0.43% (**Table 3**). Four haplotypes were detected, differing by 1-7 substitutions (**Fig. 1**). Out of Lithuanian COI haplotypes, all of them (H3, H4) were unique.

****Pineus orientalis*** (DREYFUS, 1888).

Common in Europe. Host alternating between *Picea orientalis* and *Pinus*. Closely related to *P. pini*, morphs of both species on *Pinus* are indistinguishable (see below). New finding for the fauna of Lithuania. Our samples were from *Pinus orientalis* in Coastal Lowland (Klaipėda County).

Pineus pini (MACQUART, 1819).

Common throughout Europe. Anholocyclic on *Pinus sylvestris* and *Pinus mugo*, attacking the current year's shoots. Morphologically indistinguishable from the pine inhabiting generations of *P. orientalis*. The species was already reported as inhabiting *Pinus sylvestris* at the Middle Lithuanian Lowland (Kaunas County) by RUPAIS & JURONIS (1983) and Coastal Lowland (the Curonian spit) by RAKAUSKAS *et al.* (2008). Our samples were from *Pinus sylvestris* (all geographical regions of Lithuania, except Samogitian Upland), also *P. mugo* and *P. sibirica* (in Coastal Lowland). COI sequences fail to recognize *P. pini* and *P. orientalis* species (ŽUROVCOVÁ *et al.* 2010). We used 9 partial COI sequences (657 bp) extracted from Lithuanian samples of *P. orientalis* – *pini* species complex, together with 15 of downloaded sequences (**Table 2**) in our analyses. Average proportion of differences (p-distances) within this species was 0.12% (**Table 3**). Seven haplotypes were detected in this species complex, differing by 1-6 substitutions (**Fig. 1**). Five haplotypes (H3-H7) were unique, while the other one (H2) was the same with samples from Czech Republic. Our data coincide with those of ŽUROVCOVÁ *et al.* (2010). Current knowledge suggests the conclusion that *P. pini* and *P. orientalis* should be treated as subspecies or host races of the same species.

Sacchiphantes abietis (LINNAEUS, 1758).

Common throughout Europe. Anholocyclic on *Picea* spp., with only two generations per year. Reference data from Lithuania go back to the beginning of the last century. Numerous findings of galls on *Picea excelsa* (= *P. abies*) were reported from Anykščiai (TRZEBINSKI 1916), Trakai (OSTROWSKI 1927), and Vilnius (MOVŠOVIČIUS 1941) Counties of Baltic Highlands geographical region of Lithuania. Some of these reports might actually concern *S. viridis* (see below). Our samples were from *Picea* (*P. abies*, *P. mariana*, *P. rubens*, *P. wilsonii*) in Middle Lithuanian Lowland (Kaunas, Kėdainiai and Vilkaviškis Counties) and Baltic Highlands (Vilnius, Trakai, Elektrėnai and Šalčininkai Counties).

Sacchiphantes viridis (RATZEBURG, 1843).

Common throughout Europe. Host alternating between *Picea* spp. and *Larix* spp. The pineapple galls on *Picea* are similar to those of *S. abietis* but open earlier, in July or early August (those of *S. abietis* – at the end of August and September). Morphological differences of two species are inconspicuous, COI sequences fail to recognize them (ŽUROVCOVÁ *et al.* 2010). Reference data from Lithuania go back to the 1962 (VENGELIAUSKAITĖ 1962) reporting the species as a pest of *Picea* and *Larix* in Kaunas botanical gardens. RUPAIS & JURONIS (1983) also reported severe attacks on *Picea glauca* at the same location. MOVŠOVIČIUS' (1941) report of numerous galls of *S. abietis* on *Picea excelsa* (= *P. abies*) early in the season (end of July) might concern in fact *S. viridis*. Our samples were from *Picea abies* and *P. glauca* throughout all geographical regions of Lithuania, except Coastal Lowland and Southeastern Plain. COI sequences

Table 1. The detailed collection information and GenBank accession numbers of Adelgidae species samples from Lithuania. Aphid morphs: exu – apterous or winged exulids that lives on the secondary host; gal – winged gallicola developing in gall on the primary host; gallarv – larval stages of future gallicolae in the gall on *Picea*. Geographical regions of Lithuania: Coastal – Coastal Lowland, Samogup – Samogitian Upland, MidLith – Middle Lithuanian Lowland, Baltnhigh – Baltic Highlands, Southeast – Southeastern Plain.

Host plant	Morph	Locality	County	Region	Date	Voucher No	GB accession numbers/COI
<i>Aphrastasia pectinatae</i> (CHOLODKOVSKY, 1888)							
<i>Abies concolor</i>	exu	Vilnius	Vilnius	Baltnhigh	2008-07-31	08HA-3345	GU571012
<i>Abies lasiocarpa</i>	exu	Kairėnai	Vilnius	Baltnhigh	2018-05-01	Da18-008	MH923978
<i>Abies</i> sp.	exu	Mazeikiiai	Mazeikiiai	Samogup	2018-06-20	Da18-295	MH923977
<i>Cholodkovskya viridana</i> (CHOLODKOVSKY, 1896)							
<i>Larix kaempferi</i>	exu	Klaipėda	Klaipėda	Coastal	2018-06-15	Da18-270	MH923979
<i>Larix</i> sp.	exu	Juodkrantė	Neringa	Coastal	2018-06-13	Da18-250	MH923980
<i>Larix</i> sp.		Juodkrantė	Neringa	Coastal	2018-06-14	Da18-256	MH923981
<i>Larix</i> sp.		Kaunas	Kaunas	MidLith	2018-06-06	Da18-188	MH923982
<i>Dreyfusia piceae</i> (RATZEBURG, 1844)							
<i>Abies veitchii</i>	exu	Klaipėda	Klaipėda	Coastal	2018-05-26	Da18-126	MH923983
<i>Abies alba</i>	exu	Juodkrantė	Neringa	Coastal	2018-06-14	Da 18-251	MH923984
<i>Abies</i> sp.	exu	Plungė	Plungė	Samogup	2018-07-10	Da18-331	MH923985
<i>Gilletteella cooleyi</i> (GILLETTE, 1907)							
<i>Picea pungens</i>	gal	Lazdijai	Lazdijai	Southeast	2018-07-05	Da18-308	MH923998
	gal	Joniškis	Joniškis	MidLith	2018-07-10	Da18-340	MH923999
	gal	Utena	Utena	Baltnhigh	2018-07-17	Da18-354	MH924000
<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>	exu	Klaipėda	Klaipėda	Coastal	2018-06-11	Da18-211	MH924003
	exu	Raseiniai	Raseiniai	MidLith	2018-07-08	Da18-320	MH924002

Host plant	Morph	Locality	County	Region	Date	Voucher No	GB accession numbers/COI
	exu	Rokiškis	Rokiškis	Balthigh	2018-07-17	Da18-362	MH923997
	exu	Kaunas	Kaunas	MidLith	2018-06-06	Da18-189	MH923997
<i>Pinus cembra</i> (CHOLODKOVSKY, 1888)							
<i>Pinus cembra</i>	exu	Kairėnai	Vilnius	Balthigh	2018-05-01	Da18-009	MH923987
<i>Pinus sibirica</i>	exu	Klaipėda	Klaipėda	Coastal	2017-06-12	Da17-234	MH923986
<i>Pinus orientalis</i> (DREYFUS, 1888)							
<i>Picea orientalis</i>	gal	Klaipėda	Klaipėda	Coastal	2018-06-20	Da18-284	MH923989
<i>Picea orientalis</i>	gal	Klaipėda	Klaipėda	Coastal	2018-05-26	Da18-125	MH923988
<i>Pinus pini</i> (GOEZE, 1778)							
<i>Pinus mugo</i>	exu	Joniškis	Joniškis	MidLith	2018-07-10	Da18-342B	MH923993
	exu	Klaipėda	Klaipėda	Coastal	2018-05-26	Da18-124	MH923996
	exu	Leipalingis	Druskinkinkai	Southeast	2018-05-18	Da18-57 B	MH923995
	exu	Viešintos	Anykščiai	Balthigh	2018-05-21	Da18-82	MH923990
	exu	Kalnuotė	Vilnius	Balthigh	2018-05-21	Da18-98	MH923991
	exu	Alksnynė	Neringa	Coastal	2018-05-25	Da18-120	MH923992
	exu	Rūda	Vilkaviškis	MidLith	2018-06-08	Da18-197	MH923994
<i>Adelges laricis</i> (VALLOT, 1836) - <i>tardus</i> (DREYFUS, 1888) species complex							
<i>Picea abies</i>	gal	Kernavė	Širvintos	Balthigh	2018-06-06	Da18-182	MH923949
	gal	Kaunas	Kaunas	MidLith	2018-06-06	Da18-187	MH923951
	gal	Palanga	Palanga	Coast	2018-06-15	Da18-271	MH923950
	gal	Pabradvė	Švenčionys	Balthigh	2017-08-18	Da17-597A	MH923938
	gal	Jašiūnai	Šalčininkai	Southeast	2017-08-19	Da17-602A	MH923939
	gal	Paluknys	Trakai	Balthigh	2017-08-19	Da17-609B	MH923940
	gal	Duonelaičiai	Vilkaviškis	Balthigh	2017-08-23	Da17-617A	MH923941

Host plant	Morph	Locality	County	Region	Date	Voucher No	GB accession numbers/COI
	gal	Girionys	Kaunas	MidLith	2017-08-24	Da17-620B Da17-625A Da18-368 Da18-385A Da18-398B	MH923942
	gal	Skinderiškis	Kėdainiai	MidLith	2017-08-24		MH923943
	gal	Rokiškis	Rokiškis	Baltnhigh	2018-07-17		MH923952
	gal	Kursėnai	Šiauliai	MidLith	2018-07-23		MH923953
	gal	Panevėžys	Panevėžys	MidLith	2018-07-24		MH923954
<i>Adelges laricis</i> (VALLOT, 1836)							
<i>Larix</i> sp.	exu	Marijampolė	Marijampolė	MidLith	2018-06-04	Da18-171 Da18-175 Da18-220 Da18-296 Da18-302	MH923946
	exu	Kairėnai	Vilnius	BaltHigh	2018-06-04		MH923944
	exu	Nida	Neringa	Coastal	2018-06-12		MH923945
	exu	Mazeikiai	Mazeikiai	Samogup	2018-06-20		MH923947
	gal	Lazdijai	Lazdijai	Southeast	2018-06-23		MH923948
<i>Sacchiphantes abietis</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758) - <i>viridis</i> (RAITZBURG, 1843) species complex							
<i>Picea abies</i>	gal	Pavištytis	Vilkaviškis	Baltnhigh	2017-08-15	Da17-577 Da17-546A Da17-584A Da17-589 Da17-595A Da17-604B Da17-610 Da17-614A Da17-616A Da17-621A Da17-625E Da17-628A	MH923966
	gal	Kapčiamiestis	Lazdijai	Southeast	2017-08-07		MH923956
	gal	Varteliai	Vilkaviškis	Baltnhigh	2017-08-15		MH923957
	gal	Kairėnai	Vilnius	Baltnhigh	2017-08-17		MH923959
	gal	Raudondvaris	Vilnius	Baltnhigh	2017-08-17		MH923961
	gal	Jasūnai	Šalčininkai	Southeast	2017-08-19		MH923962
	gal	Paluknys	Trakai	Baltnhigh	2017-08-19		MH923967
	gal	Geibonys	Elektrėnai	Baltnhigh	2017-08-22		MH923963
	gal	Duonelaičiai	Vilkaviškis	Baltnhigh	2017-08-23		MH923964
	gal	Girionys	Kaunas	MidLith	2017-08-24		MH923968
	gal	Skinderiškis	Kėdainiai	MidLith	2017-08-24		MH923970
	gal	Skinderiškis	Kėdainiai	MidLith	2017-08-24		MH923971

Host plant	Morph	Locality	County	Region	Date	Voucher No	GB accession numbers/COI
	gal	Rokiškis	Rokiškis	Baltnhigh	2018-07-17	Da18-366a	MH923975
	gallarv	Šiauliai	Šiauliai	Baltnhigh	2018-07-17	Da18-336	MH923976
<i>Picea maritana</i>	gal	Kairėnai	Vilnius	Baltnhigh	2017-08-17	Da17-591	MH923960
<i>Picea rubens</i>	gal	Girionys	Kaunas	Baltnhigh	2017-08-24	Da17-622C	MH923969
<i>Picea wilsonii</i>	gal	Kairėnai	Vilnius	Baltnhigh	2017-08-17	Da17-587	MH923958
<i>Sacchiphantes viridis</i> (RAITZBURG, 1843)							
<i>Larix</i> sp.	gal	Rokiškis	Rokiškis	Baltnhigh	2018-07-17	Da18-361	MH923972
	gal	Kursėnai	Šiauliai	MidLith	2018-07-23	Da18-384	MH923973
	gal	Alytus	Alytus	Southeast	2018-07-28	Da18-400	MH923974
<i>Larix decidua</i>	exu	Kapčiamiestis	Lazdijai	Southeast	2017-05-18	Da17-31	MH923965
<i>Larix decidua</i>	exu	Kairėnai	Vilnius	Baltnhigh	2017-05-18	Da17-36	MH923955

Table 2. COI haplotypes (657 bp) of 11 species of the family Adelgidae. Sample information is given in Table 1. Additional sequences GU570998-GU571051 are from ŽUROVCOVÁ *et al.* (2010), JN810887-JN810896 from TOENSHOFF *et al.* (2012a), HQ668155-HQ668157 from TOENSHOFF *et al.* (2012b).

Haplotype number	Number of sequences	Sequences belonging to haplotype
<i>Adelges laricis</i> (VALLOT, 1836) and <i>Adelges tardus</i> (DREYFUS, 1888) species complex		
1	6	GU571001, GU570998, GU571007, GU571006, JN810890, Da18-271
2	6	GU571000, GU571008, Da18-187, Da18-302, Da18-171, Da18-175
3	1	GU570999
4	1	GU571011
5	4	GU571010, GU571009, GU571004, Da18-368
6	1	GU571002
7	1	JN810896
8	1	JN810892
9	6	Da17-625A, Da17-620B, Da17-617A, Da17-609B, Da17-602A, Da18-398B
10	1	Da17-17-597A
11	1	Da18-385A
12	2	Da18-182, Da18-296
13	1	Da18-220
<i>Sacchiphantes abietis</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758) and <i>Sacchiphantes viridis</i> (RATZEBURG, 1843) species complex		
1	5	GU571067, GU571066, GU571060, JN810891, JN810887
2	2	GU571065, Da17-622C
3	1	GU571064
4	1	GU571063
5	2	GU571061, GU571059
6	20	GU571058, GU571057, GU571055, GU571054, JN810893, Da17-587, Da17-584A, Da17-546A, Da17-628A, Da17-625E, Da17-621A, Da17-577, Da17-614A, Da17-595A, Da17-591, Da17-31, Da17-36, Da18-400, Da18-384, Da18-361
7	1	GU571056
8	1	Da17-616A
9	1	Da17-604B
10	1	Da17-589
11	1	Da17-610
12	1	Da18-336
13	1	Da18-366B
<i>Aphrastasia pectinatae</i> (CHOLODKOVSKY, 1888)		
1	2	GU571012, Da18-295
2	1	Da18-008

Haplotype number	Number of sequences	Sequences belonging to haplotype
<i>Cholodkovskya viridana</i> (CHOLODKOVSKY, 1896)		
1	5	GU571015, GU571014, GU571013, Da18-188, Da18-256
2	1	Da18-250
3	1	Da18-270A
<i>Dreyfusia piceae</i> (RATZEBURG, 1844) and <i>Dreyfusia nordmanniana</i> species complex		
1	7	GU571021, GU571020, GU571019, GU571023, GU571022, HQ668157, Da18-251
2	3	GU571018, GU571017, HQ668155
3	1	GU571016
4	3	GU571024, Da18-331, Da18-126
<i>Pineus pini</i> (GOEZE, 1778) and <i>Pineus orientalis</i> (DREYFUS, 1888) species complex		
1	1	GU571089
2	17	GU571088, GU571087, GU571086, GU571085, GU571084, Da18-342B, GU571082, GU571081, GU571080, GU571079, GU571078, GU571077, GU571076, GU571075, GU571074, Da18-125, Da18-284
3	1	Da18-124
4	1	Da18-082
5	2	Da18-098, Da18-120
6	1	Da18-057B
7	1	Da18-197
<i>Pineus cembrae</i> (CHOLODKOVSKY, 1888)		
1	4	GU571073, GU571071, GU571070, GU571069
2	1	GU571072
3	1	Da18-009
4	1	Da17-234
<i>Gilletteella cooleyi</i> (GILLETTE, 1907) and <i>Gilletteella coweni</i> species complex		
1	13	GU571049, GU571047, GU571046, GU571045, GU571044, GU571043, GU571040, Da18-211, Da18-320, Da18-362, Da18-340, Da18-308, Da18-189
2	1	GU571048
3	1	GU571052
4	2	GU571050, JN810888
5	1	Da18-354

fail to recognize *S. abietis* and *S. viridis* (ŽUROVCOVÁ *et al.* 2010). We used 22 partial COI sequences (657 bp) extracted from Lithuanian samples, together with 16 of downloaded sequences (**Table 2**) in our analyses. Average proportion of differences (p-distances) within *Sacchiphantes* species was 0.35% (**Table 3**). Thirteen haplotypes were detected in this species complex, differing by 1-11 substitutions (**Fig. 1**). Out of Lithuanian COI haplotypes, 6 of them (H8-H13) were unique, while others were the same with samples from Czech Republic (H2, H6) and Austria (H6). Our data coincide with those of ŽUROVCOVÁ *et al.* 2010. Current knowledge suggests the conclusion that *S. abietis* and *S. viridis* should be treated as subspecies or host races of the same species.

Table 3. Average and range of pairwise within-species sample divergences (p-distances) of partial COI sequences (652 bp) for 11 species of the family Adelgidae.

Species	Number of samples	Average; range of divergence, %	Number of haplotypes
<i>Adelges laricis</i> and <i>A. tardus</i> species complex	32	0.43; 0.00 – 1.22	13
<i>Aphrastasia pectinatae</i>	3	0.30; 0.00 – 0.46	2
<i>Cholodkovskya viridana</i>	7	0.38; 0.00 – 1.07	3
<i>Dreyfusia piceae</i> and <i>D. nordmannianae</i> species complex	14	0.19; 0.00 – 0.76	4
<i>Gilletteella cooleyi</i> and <i>G. coweni</i> species complex	18	0.19; 0.00 – 0.76	5
<i>Pineus cembrae</i>	7	0.43; 0.00 – 1.07	4
<i>Pineus orientalis</i> and <i>P. pini</i> species complex	24	0.12; 0.00 – 0.46	7
<i>Sacchiphantes abietis</i> and <i>S. viridis</i> species complex	38	0.35; 0.00 – 3.35	13

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